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Why the Industry is Losing Faith in HSE Awards? 250 Professionals Rethink!

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Health, safety, and environment (HSE) systems are at the crossroads while in each country hundreds of people are killed while working each year. This paper questions whether the HSE awards failed to recognize or promote best safety practices in organizations? Safety awards in the industry are for business excellence and/or safety excellence. This article explores the underlying reasons for HSE Awards through a research qualitative analysis involving 250 HSE professionals. Ten main themes were identified, the implications of which are discussed for promoting a positive safety culture. About 80% of professionals agreed that the industry was losing interest as HSE awards are merely document-based, the evaluation criteria are poor, and the awards are commercial.

Introduction

Rewards give false value to a company; a business head of a multi-national company (MNC) emphasized (R. S. Rajan, personal communication, July 27, 2020). Why do we need the awards in the very first place other than for excellence recognition or bench-marking, when the safety systems are functional, being implemented and total employee participation is fully active in risk-correction at all work areas of the site or plant? Possibly, these awards can be used as a framework to follow when safety systems are in place but not fully functional. Secondly, the safety awards in the industry are used to balance business excellence and safety excellence, but more so for promoting business excellence and less for safety excellence. This divided focus could be a prime reason behind the people being killed at some workplaces despite winning HSE awards.

Every year the British Safety Council invites people to attend their awards ceremony to celebrate health and safety excellence across all industries in more than 50 countries worldwide (British Safety Council, 2020). The Confederation of Indian Industry's SHE Award is to evaluate an Organization's interest towards the wellbeing of its employees through adequate measures, not only for the regulatory requirements but also as a part of the Management's commitment towards ensuring that the workforce is adequately protected through effective Safety, Health & Environment measures (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2020). The Confederation of Indian Industry National Occupational Health & Safety Awards recognize best practices in OHS (Indian Chamber of Commerce, 2020). The National Safety

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Council awards are given annually to individuals and organizations that have demonstrated leadership in keeping people safe at workplaces (National Safety Council of India, 2020). Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry emphasizes safety systems excellence awards every year or Industry (FICCI, 2020). The Government of India instituted National Safety Awards (NSA) in the year 1965, to recognize the safety performance of Industries to maintain the interest of both the management and the workers in accident prevention (DGFASLI, 2020). The National Safety Council of America offers a variety of individual, team, and corporate awards. Employers providing exemplary on-the-job safety and health programs are eligible for the Community Safety Award (NSC, 2020). The safety awards programs provide companies, a means to gauge their program against the industry it does business in.

“Critically speaking, there is a huge number of at-risk behaviors at every site and the companies still receive safety awards, this highlights doubts about the validity of such awards” (Kaila, 2011, p. 2135).

Research Question / Objective Statement

The research objective was to explore the perceptions and reasons, to determine whether the people in the industry are losing faith in HSE awards, and to suggest the scope for improving various aspects of HSE awards management.

Methodology

Open-ended questions based on interviews and personal in-depth discussions with 250 HSE, medical, education, management, and mental health professionals were conducted through remote data collection techniques over 3 months (July-September 2020) in India from diverse locations and organizations. The responses of these professionals are presented in the following 10 themes.

Research Findings

About 80% agreed that they are losing interest or lost interest in applying for an Award as an Award is only document-based evidence of excellence, and also it would depend on the type of national or international, private or government agencies providing Awards, their evaluation criteria, but mostly commercial awards are being avoided, as stated by HSE professionals interviewed. Ten insightful aspects of 250 research participants' views on safety awards are described below.

1. Awards are Ornamental with not much value

The value of safety awards was questioned as being only ornamental for organizations. The responses received from 80 percent of the HSE professionals indicate that there is not much value in the HSE awards. They have become ornaments to showcase excellence in workplace safety management. According to a safety head, “I have all and sundry associations giving safety awards without doing any review. I do know, where just after a fatal incident, the organizations showcase safety awards from Delhi association”. An objective and thorough methodology of assessment is needed to bring in faith for these awards.

The safety awards to Massey Energy and Transocean were questioned after the coal and oil disasters (The Rural Blog, 2010). In relation to the oil disaster, the Deepwater Horizon was owned by Transocean but was under lease to British Petroleum (BP). For work on the Deepwater Horizon BP chose risky procedures to save time and money, often against the advice of staff and contractors. For example, BP replaces the drilling mud with lighter seawater even though the rig's chief driller protested. BP did not rectify well design problems when warned of these by the subcontractors. “BP

made choices that set safety aside in exchange for cost-cutting and timesaving decisions” (US Government Committee on Energy and Commerce, 2010, p.14). Transocean blamed the disaster on a flawed well design by BP.

The value addition of awards schemes that exist in the Occupational Health and Safety area is very limited (Hopkins & Gervis, 2006). These schemes can result in safety behaviors if they are focused, well implemented, and evaluated.

2. Rationale of Awards

This study results reveal that the organizations are not only losing faith in safety awards, but they are also generally worried about so many useless awards (about 84% of all types of awards), being pushed for commercial purposes these days. The majority of corporates are choosy and don't even apply for many such awards. Many organizations lack in sincere, honest, ethical approach in filling up the awards application. Even, the awarding agencies are interested in nothing more than the commercial aspects. (A. Garg, personal communication, July 20, 2020).

3. Criteria, fee and assessment are important

Nearly 100 percent of HSE professionals emphasized that safety awards should be provided to organizations and the people who really demonstrate safety in the field. If the mechanism of giving a safety award is not sound, then one can face the problem of losing faith in the Safety Awards. According to a safety manager, “people are losing faith, as nowadays safety awards are linked with entry fees. In some awards, even assessment processes are also not up to the mark” (V. Maheashwaran, personal communication, July 30, 2020). “But yes, some awards are really worth due to their assessment process. Some agencies are following assessment based on an application. No data verification and site assessment” (R. Narayan, personal communication, July 24, 2020). The second type of assessment is based on application and data verification.

The third assessment has 3 steps which are quite comprehensive:

1. Application assessment & data verification.
2. Site assessment by independent bodies.
3. Final presentation by the organization for best practices.

The University of Iowa (2020) suggested the review criteria to include annual safety reviews, implementation of corrective actions, departments not to be penalized for reporting incidents, engagement to improve safety culture, and innovations in safety practices.

4. Fairness in Awards

Much uncertainty exists regarding the effectiveness of safety awards (Goodrum & Gangwar, 2004, p.4). A safety head stated, “recent days, there are some open biases, and also some real achievers are recognized. I see it from my own experience. We got to be non-judgmental in evaluating the contributions”. Nearly 84 percent of HSE professionals agreed that there is a huge scope of improvement in this area. It is crucial to guide organizations to provide fair information about safety performance even if it is not favorable (WorkSafe Travail Securitaire NB, 2020).

5. Reputed Awarding Agencies matter

Nearly 54 percent of the HSE professionals expressed that the people believe in grabbing reputed organization awards like the Confederation of Indian Industries (CII), The Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce & Industry (FICCI), National Safety Council (NSC), and British Safety Council (BSC) which can bring laurels to their organization. The award can be a big motivational tool.

The main goal of the NSC awards is to support the broader mission to save lives and prevent injuries, from the workplace to any place (National Safety Council of India, 2020).

6. Authentic Awards do provide value

Is the Indian industry losing faith in the safety awards? “I don't think so”, as expressed by an EHS top leader of a multinational company (V. Banker, personal communication, August 14, 2020). “I am going to introduce one new award. If people are guided correctly, they are keen to work upon exact requirements in safety improvement and can achieve these awards (K. K. Sharma, personal communication, August 25, 2020). About 51 percent of the HSE professionals expressed that authentic and quality awards like that of NSC, OISD, Ministry are always welcoming. Rewards are recognition of demonstrated commitment to the safety of an organization ensuring that the workforce is adequately protected through effective HSE measures (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2020).

7. Management perspective

Research respondents (25%) said that people still have faith in safety awards as such awards boost the morale of employees and marginally increases the faith of employees in their own safety systems. However, sometimes, the management takes it from a different perspective. About 75% of the HSE professionals expressed that nowadays management is mostly sales-focused, believing in statistics to use to answer to the board for workplace safety and health effectiveness. Research respondents stated that believed that for big companies like L&T and Tata, the awards can be purchased based on providing rosy information. Management thinks that awards for safety would help build a safety culture and keep workers working safely, but awards cause disinterests for everyone except the award winner as management perspective is to use awards for sales promotions (Burns, 2020).

8. Self-realisation is the key

Over the years, the awards have motivated companies to adopt best safety practices and systems in their sector are benchmarked with the best in the industry (FICCI, 2020), but 70% of research respondents said that one has to be very critical if these best practices are only document-based. According to a veteran EHS Director, “It depends on which safety award we strive for. Getting a 5-star BSC rating is easy as it has become more of a business than an endeavor to improve industrial safety. Most of the safety awards are data-based, which is not the correct picture of the safety performance! Nearly 69 percent of the HSE professionals expressed that the self-realization and purpose behind safety drive itself is an award for the industry if each milestone achieved is celebrated, as safety is a journey and achieving every milestone brings self-satisfaction and self-appreciation to keep motivated to work safely.

9. Seeking awards for Safety Culture

According to 76% of respondents, it was important to make ‘working safely’ in a continuous manner to set a standard as this will make a benchmark for the organization in a period of time. Then that will become the culture for the organization. So setting standards and establishing the system will provide the guidelines to work more safely, continuously working in a safe manner will be leading to a better culture, by following others to follow and adhere to the same.

Fifty-two percent of corporate professionals in the research study stated that they are promoting a safety culture in their worksites across Indian locations so that they could apply and achieve national safety awards and that they are working hard to strategically plan an approach to achieve awards. It is like planning forward, implementation backward. The Toronto Construction Association's (2020) Outstanding Safety Culture Award, recognizes a company that treats safety protocols with a genuine sense of urgency and is innovative and rigorous about ensuring workplace safety is paramount.

10. Awarded sites also have serious incidents

Nearly 50 percent of the HSE professionals agreed that there are many serious incidents that happened at worksites across the globe at work premises that were certified and provided with an award by national or international agencies. This implicates several aspects, (1) that the awards are possibly limited to feel-good factor or appreciation, or (2) whether the sites get complacent after receiving these awards. A huge fire at an Indian Oil Corporation terminal was due to compromising the safety procedures (Business Standard, 2013). This workplace had achieved all national and international laurels and certifications.

The International Stainless-Steel Forum introduced a Safety Award Programme that invited members to submit good ideas from their Safety Programmes. These good ideas are then circulated among members, following the principle that people would learn from the accidents of others (Core Sector Communique, 2020). This was a useful award program.

Conclusions, Recommendations, and Implications

1. There exists a large number of HSE awards to recognize workplaces with safety excellence; nevertheless, incidents and fatalities keep on increasing. Whether these awards deliver what they stand for is a million-dollar question. Each country has hundreds of work-related fatalities each year. For example, 110 Australian workers were killed at work in 2020 till 10 September. In 2019, 182 Australian workers were fatally injured while working, whereas, 3,751 workers were fatally injured while working over the 15 year period between 2003 to 2018 with the most common reason for fatalities in 2018 being vehicle collisions on roads (Safe Work Australia, 2020). However, these fatality statistics do not record that any of the companies that had a work-related fatality had won a safety award.
2. Eighty percent of HSE professionals perceived that the industry is losing interest, or has lost interest, in safety awards, for many reasons, that include that the awards are ornamental, useless, rationale, criteria, fee, and assessment. There is much scope for improvement in being fair while providing information, having reputable awarding agencies matters, authentic awards were valued, understanding management perspective, promoting self-realization, and seeking awards for improving safety culture. Respondents also concluded that some awarded sites had serious incidents.
3. Whether the industry is losing faith in the Safety Awards? The perspective of 80% of respondents was that people who are working in developing organizations benefited because when applying any new tenders having accreditation and awards for excellence may assist with obtaining the tendered work. Secondly, whereas the developed organizations are concerned, sometimes they do not believe the awards but assess the company's HSE implementation for itself. In India, for accreditation companies mainly focus on ISO certifications to enhance their systems and HSE implementation. The DuPont Safety and Sustainability Awards invite organizations that successfully implemented innovative ways of safeguarding employees, communities, and the environment, while also contributing to the economic and social health of society to be nominated for Awards (DuPont Sustainable Solutions, 2020).

4. Seventy-five percent of respondents reported that Management focus is often on achieving business success rather than on safety when achieving national and international HSE awards and accolades. Twenty-five percent of respondents said that they knew of corporations that have awards that have subsequently had work-related fatalities. Besides awards, there are safety and occupational health experts, but accidents and fatalities still occur. Hence, 75% of study participants were of the view that safety awards are not meant to say that the organization has achieved safety excellence. Preventing workplace fatalities is a necessary goal of safety management systems, but sometimes the employers fail in their leadership roles and approach towards fatality prevention, the unthinkable happens and someone dies at the work (Walter, 2020).

Recommendations and Implications

1. SRC Communications & Johnston (2019) observed that the safety culture was more than just working safely, it was about celebrating successes and continuously improving. The critical question is that when organizations on average have an almost 30% at-risk behavior, which obviously means they lack the safety culture, then how could they be considered for safety awards? On the other hand, award agencies should consider the behavioral aspects of safety, whereby behavior is the root cause of almost all incidents (Kaila, 2020). In this regard, if the accounting of at-risk behaviors is not part of awards criteria, then these awards are not valid, and incidents would surely occur, even after receiving the best safety awards. Unsafe practices/at-risk behaviors are the early warning signs of a potentially serious incident and the zero initiative ought to include steps like targeting zero injuries, empowering individuals, creating a positive reporting culture, reporting of near misses, managing workplace incidents, commitment to sustaining a safe workplace, communicating openly, influencing long-term change (Webcke, 2020).
2. In India most of the safety awards defy the fundamentals of occupational safety and health (OSH) which is generally defined by the International Labor Organization (ILO) as recognition and control of hazards arising from the work areas that affect the health of workmen as well as the impact on the environment (Alli, 2008). In principle, a safety award based on a well-rounded evaluation is required to determine the extent to which it is intended to show that the workers are safe in their workplace (Wegman & McGee, 2004). Safety awards criteria should assess the field-level increase of safety awareness of the employer and employees annually (Yumpu, 2020).
3. Some awards in India were perceived by 83% of research participants to lack much in their application value, ethical standards, value for life, etc. Most progressive companies affirmed that their business excellence is almost 100% when their HSE excellence is nearly 70-80 percent, which is questionable in view of their value for human life and zero-harm focus. It is clear that safety awards and having a positive safety culture do not always fit together (S. Desai, personal communication, September 5, 2020). There is a need to understand the safety awards criteria in the pretext of the existing safety culture in the industry. Safety policies and procedures differ so much in practices in every plant. According to a veteran Vice President (HSE) of an MNC, "Bent for profits of the managements over-writes safety culture, 'safety first' even becomes 2nd/3rd, it is OK, but safety takes the last seat in favor of business" (A. Dvaz, personal communication, September 15, 2020). Many safety culture awards are available with well-defined criteria (Safe Work Manitoba, 2020) but incidents keep happening regularly which does not support the rationale/effectiveness of the HSE awards, particularly if an unexpected

unplanned event occurs. This is why part of emergency management is business continuity planning.

4. All Indian work sites are not totally safe, as most companies revealed their safety culture management score is around 80 percent. Awards should only be given on the basis of the following 10 points criteria measurement (Kaila, 2020).

- There is a strong belief in behavior-based safety (BBS) concepts of all employees and management and BBS is rolled out among all employees at the site/plant.
- BBS is adopted as corporate policy/value and in employee performance management.
- BBS is being practiced on a daily basis by all employees and Associates.
- Online observations reporting in each department including contractors.
- Each department has eliminated reactive and dependent safety cultures.
- Motivational rewarding for best observers and departments are provided every month.
- People at the site don't bypass unsafe behavior but spot-correct it.
- Departments are aware of the Hot Spots
- Departments have an action plan to address the Hot Spots
- Head of Department is motivating employees and associates for BBS

For many companies in India to reach a score of 100, an improvement action plan is required, especially for contractors' staff, to move from having a dependent safety culture to an independent and interdependent safety culture. In a new action plan to make a positive safety culture as a way of life, there is a need to linking BBS to corporate social responsibility (CSR), communities, and colonies around as well as homes. Building a Safe System is a holistic, long-term exercise, and is based on shared responsibility (ITF, 2016).

According to an HSE Strategist, (S. Rao, personal communication, September 30, 2020), the HSE awards need to consider the following:

- Vision Zero can be achieved only if the BBS processes are meticulously followed;
- BBS - A Key element needs to include in HSE as the Key element in all industries.
- HSE guidelines need to be redefined in light of this global pandemic with BBS playing a key role.
- BBS influencing HIRA strategies inculcating responsible behavior in the minds of workers.
- BBS training shall be mandatory in the training calendar of every Industry.

According to AFCONS, Gopalpur Port Project, the Winner in CII (Confederation of Indian Industry) eastern region Safety, Health & Environment Award 2019-2020 (which achieved a higher score than the other 9 Construction companies that applied for this Award), "if you follow BBS guidelines, you can win every platform" (P. Mukerjee, personal communication, September 25, 2020). A senior professor at the National Institute of Industrial Engineering (NITIE) stated, "BBS reinforces the traditional safety systems aiming towards zero incidences in the workplace".

5. Eighty percent of research participants said that there was a low concern for safety for the contractors' staff. The absence of workplace protections reflects on the efforts to undermine worker safety (Leibenluft and Olinsky, 2020). According to 80% of research participants, most organizations admitted that they are able to develop a safety culture for their employees but failed to do so for contractors' workmen and asked how these companies receive the awards when the benefit of positive safety culture has not been reached for all people at the work

premises of the company. Hence, there needs to be a planned intervention to improve safety awareness among the low-paid contractual persons.

6. According to 50% of research participants practically, the corporates in India are not ready for safety awards, as they have not established a safety culture at sites for which they are awarded. There is a widespread failure to take safety regulations seriously (Dorrell, 2003). Sixty percent of participants said that the awarding agencies take this opportunity to award them for vested commercial interests. Proactively, either the companies must achieve safe workplaces and then go for awards, and/or the awarding agencies must enable, support, and develop the safety cultures and then award these aspiring applicants for awards. According to 50% of research participants, many corporations in India have stopped taking interest in these awards but are trying hard to remain focused on developing safe workplaces for their workforce as nobody likes to get even a first-aid injury.
7. Finally, the serious implications of the findings of this research can be imagined in terms of fake awards based on rosy information of safety leading to incidents of fire or fatalities sounding very critical in nature. While this scenario endangers the lives of people to the unmitigated risks that the employees and contract staff are exposed to. The role of the HSE is questioned in preventing accidents at work which would lead to more injuries and possibly lost lives (PFM, 2020). With these fake/so-called HSE awards being received based on mere documentation leading to a better image of the company for more sales promotions and insurance coverage for being awarded/certified sites, are some complications and violations of business ethos.
8. The benefits that the effective Board level ethics, organizational vision, leadership, and direction of occupational health and safety can bring in terms of health and safety of people and the overall business performance are inseparable. Then why is it that the business excellence is far ahead, and, the HSE excellence is far behind which puts the lives of employees at greater risks killing people each year? The organizations aspiring awards and the HSE awards agencies need to revisit this imbalance seriously in terms of ground realities of safe practices (Health and Safety Executive, 2006).
9. It is recommendable in view of the above proceedings of this paper that a company having weak safety culture should not be awardable, and awarding such an entity should be unlawful and to be avoided by the awarding agencies. It is hoped that these implications shall be interpreted positively as a piece of research information towards a scope of improvement in HSE awards for corporate safety and human life.
10. In view of the above discussions, there is a strong need felt for local governments' control over the wrongful selection criteria on the safety awards in India, and installing corrective action on agencies awarding companies with unsafe HSE cultures, in the larger interest of the society for developing safe systems based on innovation and excellence (Australian Government, 2020), and finally, to probe a vital question as to why so routinely the ethics of human safety are being sandwiched and bypassed between business profits and safety excellence, and someone gets killed.

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